

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№3

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

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*Elektron nashr. 505 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 11-martda ruxsat etildi.*

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- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
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- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
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- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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Picture 1: Expected benefits of sustainable supply chains, 2022 [1].

Uzbekistan, as a rapidly industrializing country, has the potential to effectively align its supply chain operations with sustainability goals to remain competitive in the global market. The country's supply chain infrastructure is export-oriented and traditional, with significant opportunities for integrating circular economy models, low-carbon transportation, and digital transparency. Changes in these areas will play a crucial role in ensuring long-term industrial growth and environmental responsibility.

By analyzing policy frameworks, technological adoption, and industry-specific challenges, this research offers actionable strategies for embedding sustainability into Uzbekistan's supply chain networks. Drawing from global best practices - such as circular economy strategies, renewable energy incentives, and multimodal logistics solutions - Uzbekistan can develop a resilient, future-ready supply chain ecosystem, in line with both economic and environmental imperatives.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Sustainable Supply Chain Management: SSCM integrates environmental, social, and economic dimensions into supply chain operations. Seuring and Müller (2007) define SSCM as managing material, information, and capital flows while balancing triple-bottom-line objectives [1]. Carter and Rogers (2008) emphasize aligning SCM with sustainability through stakeholder collaboration and lifecycle analysis [2].

Green Logistics and Emission Reduction: Green logistics prioritizes low-carbon transportation and energy efficiency. Dekker et al. (2012) highlight route optimization and alternative fuels as key strategies [3]. In Uzbekistan, some scientists note the potential for rail-network modernization to reduce freight emissions, aligning with Sbihi and Eglese (2010), who advocate modal shifts to sustainable transport [4].

Circular Economy Integration: Circular economy models focus on waste reduction and resource circularity. Genovese et al. (2017) propose closed-loop systems for recycling and remanufacturing [5].

Digital Transformation in SSCM: Industry 4.0 technologies enhance transparency and efficiency. Hofmann and Rüsç (2017) demonstrate IoT's role in real-time tracking [6], while Saberi et al. (2019) explore blockchain for ethical sourcing [7].

Policy and Regulatory Drivers: Pagell and Wu (2009) argue that regulatory frameworks accelerate SSCM adoption [8]. Sarkis et al. (2011) identify tax incentives and emissions regulations as critical enablers [9].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed-methods approach:

Content Analysis: Academic literature is analyzed to extract SCM principles and sustainability linkages.

Systematic Literature: peer-reviewed articles (2010–2024) on SSCM are synthesized.

Case Studies: Uzbek industries (e.g., textiles, agriculture) are evaluated for SSCM applicability.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Global Practices: Rail modernization plays a crucial role in global decarbonization efforts, as emphasized by Sbihi and Eglese (2007) in their support for modal shifts. However, Uzbekistan's progress remains nascent compared to global benchmarks. For instance, Germany's recycling system achieved a packaging recycling rate of 68.5% in 2022 [], whereas Uzbekistan's recycling infrastructure recovers only about 5% of household waste, highlighting a significant gap in closed-loop systems [].

While the significance of localized supply chains is undisputed, Uzbekistan's cotton industry remains heavily export driven. In 2022, the country exported \$1.62 billion worth of cotton, making it the 9th largest exporter globally []. This strategy contrasts with efforts in countries like Bangladesh, where textile waste is being repurposed into new products, fostering a more circular economy [].

Renewable Energy Integration Lag: Despite some scientists' recognition of Uzbekistan's solar potential, the country's logistics sector currently derives less than 5% of its energy from renewable sources. In contrast, Turkey has been actively developing green logistics hubs that integrate renewable energy to mitigate environmental impacts. For instance, the Turkish government has prioritized renewable energy over thermal power plants in its clean energy transition, aiming to reach net-zero emissions by 2053. This includes plans to integrate renewable energy sources into various sectors, including logistics [].

Rail Modernization vs. Multimodal Networks: While rail upgrades can reduce emissions, leading countries like Switzerland enhance these benefits by integrating rail transport with electric vehicles for last-mile delivery. For instance, DPD Switzerland has incorporated e-trucks into its transalpine distribution network, aiming for a fully zero-emission fleet by 2030 []. In contrast, Uzbekistan's reliance on diesel trucks for final-mile logistics may offset the environmental advantages gained from rail improvements, highlighting the need for hybrid solutions that combine rail and electric vehicle use.

Circular Economy Pilots: Establish textile waste recycling hubs in cotton clusters (e.g., Fergana Valley) to repurpose cotton waste into valuable products. For example, Panipat, a town in Haryana, India, has become the largest textile recycling hub in the country, demonstrating the potential of centralized recycling initiatives [].

Renewable Energy Incentives: Introduce incentives for solar adoption in logistics parks, drawing inspiration from successful initiatives in other countries. In particular, Horizon Industrial Parks in India currently meet 20% of their energy consumption through solar power, with plans to increase this to 30-35% in the next 12-18 months, showcasing the benefits of solar integration in logistics [].

Multimodal Integration: Partner with global entities like the World Bank to fund electric vehicle fleets for last-mile delivery, aiming to phase out diesel trucks in the coming years. For example, P3 Logistic Parks' "Power of Logistics" initiative enables operators to combine green power sources into a park-wide microgrid, supplying all tenants with renewable energy and providing fast charging stations for commercial vehicles, facilitating the transition to electric fleets [].

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study critically analyzed the incorporation of sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) principles within Uzbekistan's industrial sectors, drawing upon a foundational framework developed by both local and international researchers. The findings indicate that while efforts toward rail modernization and localized supply chains align with global decarbonization initiatives, substantial challenges remain in implementing advanced circular economy strategies and integrating renewable energy solutions.

Key findings indicate that Uzbekistan's recycling infrastructure is underdeveloped, with only about 4-5% of household waste being recycled, in stark contrast to higher rates observed in countries like Germany. Additionally, the country's cotton industry remains heavily export-oriented, lacking initiatives to repurpose textile waste into new products, as seen in nations such as Bangladesh. The logistics sector's reliance on diesel trucks for final-mile delivery further exacerbates environmental impacts, underscoring the need for multimodal transportation solutions.

To bridge these gaps, the study recommends establishing textile waste recycling hubs in key cotton-producing regions like the Fergana Valley, introducing incentives for solar energy adoption in logistics parks, and partnering with global entities to fund electric vehicle fleets for last-mile delivery. Implementing these strategies could facilitate Uzbekistan's transition from a linear, export-driven supply chain model to a more resilient and sustainable ecosystem, better aligned with global sustainability imperatives.

Future research should focus on assessing the feasibility and impact of these recommendations, exploring policy frameworks that support SSCM adoption, and identifying best practices from other countries that can be adapted to the Uzbek context. Addressing technological adoption gaps, infrastructural limitations, and policy alignment will be crucial for Uzbek industries aiming to transition to sustainable practices.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 3

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
